

Synthesis of Some New 4(3H)Quinazolinones as Potential Fungicides

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Several 6,8-disubstituted-2-phenyl-3[(substituted)benzothiazol-2'-yl]-4(3H)quinazolinones have been synthesised. Their fungicidal activity has been screened on *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Alternaria alternata*. 6-Methyl, 5 and 6-chloro substituted derivatives have been found to be very good fungicides.

SEVERAL biological activities have been reported in 4(3H)quinazolinones¹⁻⁵ which have been successfully screened as antihypertensives⁶, chlorectic, antifibrillatory, antiphlogistic, hypotensive⁷, antiadrenergic, antihistaminic⁸, antifungal⁹⁻¹⁰, herbicidal¹¹ and bactericidal¹² agents. Febrifugine, an alkaloid with a 3-substituted 4(3H)quinazolinone structure has been found to be antimalarial¹³. Siamian and avian malarial infections have also been successfully treated with them^{14,15}. Viricidal activity has been reported in some nitro substituted 4-quinazolinone derivatives¹⁶. Oine *et al*¹⁷ have prepared some quinazolinones with antiulcer, CNS depressant and analgesic action. Some piperizino quinazolinones as cardiovascular, hypotensive, nor-adrenalin inhibiting, brady-cardiac and trachycardiac agents have recently been reported by Dubey *et al*¹⁸. Antitumour and anticancerous actions have also been observed in 2-alkyl-3-aryl-4-(3H)quinazolinone derivatives¹⁹. Hutchinson *et al*²⁰ have reported antileukemic activity in 4(3H)quinazolinone derivatives. The findings of Peck *et al*^{21,22} and Creech *et al*²³ have considerably accelerated the investigation with this system.

Various heterocyclic systems have been attached to the quinazolinone system at positions two and three. The search for potential psychotropic agents led to the preparation of 2-(N⁴-arylpiperazino carbonylmethylthio)-3-aryl-6-bromo-4(3H)quinazolinones²⁴. Recently Pandey *et al*²⁵ have synthesised 2-aryl (or alkyl)-3-(2'-aminomethyl-1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-5'-yl)quinazol-4(3H)-ones as potential anti-parkinsonian compounds. Amoebicidal and fungicidal activities have been reported in some quinazolinone derivatives by Gupta *et al*²⁶.

Keeping in view the wide spectrum activities of this system it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some 4(3H)quinazolinones incorporating the substituted benzothiazole moiety at position three as possible antifungal agents. The com-

pounds were prepared according to the scheme outlined below :

6, 8-Disubstituted-2-phenyl-3-[(substituted)benzothiazol-2'-yl]-4(3H)quinazolinones were obtained through benzoxazinone intermediate by refluxing substituted 2-amino benzothiazoles with 3, 5-disubstituted N-benzoyl anthranilic acids and phosphorous trichloride in toluene for 4 hr. The structure was confirmed by elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectra.

Experimental

All melting points were recorded in open capillary in liquid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer, nmr on Varian A-60 D Model at 60 Hz at 45°. A Coleman analyser was used for elemental analysis.

N-Benzoylanthranilic acid and 3,5-dibromo-N-benzoylanthranilic acid were prepared by known methods^{27,28}.

Substituted 2-amino benzothiazoles : These were prepared by the oxidation of asymmetrical aryl thiourea with liquid bromine in chloroform²⁹.

6,8-Dibromo-2-phenyl-3-(6'-ethoxy benzothiazol-2'-yl)-4(3H)quinazolinone : A mixture of benzoyl anthranilic acid (7.5 g), 2-amino-6-ethoxy benzothiazole (3.30 g), phosphorous trichloride (1.5 ml)

TABLE 1—6,8-DISUBSTITUTED-2-PHENYL-3-[(SUBSTITUTED)BENZOTHAZOL-2'-YL]-4(3H)QUINAZOLINONES

Sl. No.	Substituents		Molecular Formula	Yield %	m.p. °C	Carbon %		Hydrogen %	
	X	Y=Z				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	H	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	65	101	71.16	70.98	3.70	3.66
2.	5-Me	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	81	187	71.75	71.54	3.89	4.06
3.	6-Me	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	39	167	70.27	71.54	4.26	4.06
4.	5-Cl	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	46	120	64.41	64.69	3.89	3.08
5.	6-Cl	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	49	115	64.56	64.69	2.99	3.08
6.	6-MeO	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃ S	71	116	68.71	68.57	4.01	3.89
7.	6-EtO	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ S	76	150	68.92	69.17	4.40	4.26
8.	H	Br	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	61	184	48.88	49.12	2.01	2.14
9.	5-Me	Br	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	29	194	49.87	50.09	2.39	2.46
10.	6-Me	Br	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	33	198	49.99	50.09	2.61	2.46
11.	5-Cl	Br	C ₂₁ H ₁₀ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	49	170	45.23	45.56	2.01	1.82
12.	6-Cl	Br	C ₂₁ H ₁₀ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	62	205	45.87	45.56	2.11	1.82
13.	6-MeO	Br	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ O ₃ S	69	145	48.42	48.62	2.56	2.39
14.	6-EtO	Br	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ BrN ₂ O ₃ S	73	169	49.59	49.55	2.81	2.69

and dry toluene was refluxed on water bath for 4 hr. Excess toluene was distilled off. The granular product was washed with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution and distilled water. It was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol to give 6,8-dibromo-2-phenyl-3-(6'-ethoxy benzothiazol-2'-yl)-4(3H)-quinazolinone in 73% yield; m.p. 169°. Anal. Found: C, 49.59; H, 2.81; Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₅Br₂N₂O₃S; C, 49.55; H, 2.69%. IR (nujol): 1765s, 1655m, 1600s, 1555m cm⁻¹. NMR (CDCl₃): δ: (J=Hz), 1.45(3H, t, J=7.0), 4.10(2H, q, J=7.0) and 7.1 to 8.3 for aromatic protons (10H, m).

Other 2-phenyl-3-[(substituted)benzothiazol-2'-yl]-4(3H)quinazolinones and 6,8-dibromo-2-phenyl-3-[(substituted)benzothiazol-2'-yl]-4(3H)quinazolinones were prepared similarly. Their melting points, yields and analytical data are reported in Table 1.

Biological tests: The compounds 2-phenyl-3-[(substituted)benzothiazol-2'-yl]-4(3H)quinazolinones and 6,8-dibromo-2-phenyl-3-[(substituted)benzothiazol-2'-yl]-4(3H)quinazolinones were tested for fungicidal action on *Alternaria alternata* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* by the agar plate technique²⁷ at two dilutions.

The percent inhibition of growth was determined by comparison with growth in controls and the results are recorded in Table 2. All solutions were prepared in absolute alcohol. The medium in controls and the treated plates was potato dextrose agar culture medium and the incubation time 96 hr at 28 ± 1°.

The results indicate that the activity of the compounds is of high order against both the species. The replacement of hydrogen by methyl, chloro, methoxy or ethoxy group increases the activity at both dilutions in case of the 2-phenyl derivatives. Fungicidal action decreases when the substituent is 6-methoxy in case of *Aspergillus fumigatus*. The decrease is slight at low and considerable at high dilutions.

The introduction of 6,8-dibromo group in the 4(3H)quinazolinone ring appears to enhance the antifungal properties considerably as compared to

TABLE 2—FUNGICIDAL SCREENING RESULTS OF 6,8-DISUBSTITUTED-2-PHENYL-3-[(SUBSTITUTED)BENZOTHAZOL-2'-YL]-4(3H)QUINAZOLINONES

Sl. No.	Substituents		<i>Alternaria alternata</i>		<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	
	X	Y=Z	Dilutions		Dilutions	
			1 : 1500	1 : 3400	1 : 1500	1 : 3400
1.	H	H	82	74	100	52
2.	6-Me	H	100	100	100	100
3.	5-Cl	H	100	78	100	61
4.	6-Cl	H	100	100	100	100
5.	6-MeO	H	100	74	82	39
6.	6-EtO	H	100	83	100	74
7.	H	Br	100	83	100	74
8.	5-Me	Br	100	67	100	91
9.	6-Me	Br	100	100	100	74
10.	5-Cl	Br	100	100	100	100
11.	6-Cl	Br	100	79	100	100
12.	6-MeO	Br	82	67	100	100
13.	6-EtO	Br	82	79	55	74

the non substituted derivatives. The compounds of 6,8-dibromo-2-phenyl-3-[(substituted)benzothiazol-2'-yl]-4(3H)quinazolinones inhibit 100% spore germination of both the fungal species, especially at low dilutions and appear to be potent antifungal agents. Further testing of these compounds for CNS depressant activity is in progress.

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